

powdered and extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°). The defatted stem was extracted with 95% ethanol for 25 days, and the extract (3 dm³) concentrated to a brown viscous mass was treated with methanol. The methanol soluble part was concentrated to a brown viscous mass and excess of solvent ether (250 ml) added to get a precipitate. The precipitate was purified by column chromatography over column silica gel G with acetone–methanol (3 : 1) to yield the saponin, m.p. 218°, which was found to be homogeneous by tlc in BAW (4 : 1 : 5), $R_f=0.69$.

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Chemical Constituents of *Canarium strictum* Gum

(Miss) S. MALHOTRA, S. C. TANEJA and K. L. DHAR*
Natural Products Chemistry, Regional Research Laboratory,
Canal Road, Jammu Tawi-180 001

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PLANTS of genus *Burseraceae* are well known for their economical and medicinal values¹. *Canarium strictum* gum, commonly known as Kala Dammer,

has been found as a rich source of triterpenoids². Literature review also indicated the presence of canarone apart from other terpenic compounds³.

In our present studies on its gum a new derivative of β -amyryn has been isolated along with four other compounds, which are identified as α -amyryn, β -amyryn, β -amyryn acetate and sitosterol by direct comparison.

Compound-A, m.p. 225°, isolated from petroleum ether extract was analysed for $C_{31}H_{50}O_2$. The ir spectra showed the presence of a C=O group (1720 cm⁻¹). In the ¹H nmr spectral signal for the methine proton was observed at δ 4.48 (t) and the singlet at δ 8.06 is assigned to the formyl proton. Compound-A on alkali hydrolysis afforded a compound-B, m.p. 197°, which showed the presence of OH group in the ir spectra. It was identified as β -amyryn by direct comparison. From the above studies compound-A seems to be the formyl derivative of β -amyryn. The final confirmation of the structure of compound-A was done by preparing the formate of β -amyryn and comparison of both. The mass fragmentation pattern further confirmed the structure which showed a strong $M-CO$ (426) fragment. This is the first report of the occurrence of β -amyryn formate from a natural source.

Experimental

All the m.p.s. were recorded on the Kofler block and are uncorrected. Compounds were separated by column chromatography on silica gel. Ir spectra was recorded on Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian T60A and Jeol/FX-90 spectrometers and mass spectra on a JM5D-300 spectrometer.

The air-dried powder gum (250 g) was extracted in petroleum ether. The concentrated petroleum ether extract was fractionated by column chromatography to collect five compounds. Compound-A as white needles, m.p. 225° (Found : C, 80.09 ; H, 10.9. $C_{31}H_{50}O_2$ requires : C, 81.93 ; H, 11.01%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 2900, 1720, 1540, 1275, 1200 and 780 cm⁻¹ ; δ (CDCl₃) 8.06 (1H, s, CHO), 5.06 (1H, bs, C₁₃-H), 4.48 (1H, t, J 7Hz, C₈-H), 1.6–1.02 (18H, 3H, bs, 9×CH₂) and 1.02–0.7 (24H, bs, 8×CH₃) ; m/z 454 (M^+) 426, 250, 216 and 207.

Formylation of compound-A : β -Amyryn (50 mg) was dissolved in dry ether (25 ml) and added slowly to the formylating reagent⁴ (10 ml) (prepared by adding 10 ml HCOOH to 20 ml Ac₂O at -5 to 10°) with constant stirring at 10–30°. The reaction mixture was left at the same temperature for 4 h and then poured in ice-water, extracted with CHCl₃ (3×50 ml). The CHCl₃ extract was concentrated to collect the product (40 mg) which was purified by chromatography and identified (compound-A) by m.m.p., co-tlc and superimposable ir spectra.

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Chemical Examination of *Coccinia indica* Fruits

SUJATA KUNDU and A. B. RAY*

Department of Medicinal Chemistry,
Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University,
Varanasi-221 005

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AS a part of our investigation on the chemical constituents of Indian medicinal plants, we examined the fruits of *Coccinia indica*, a plant known to possess hypoglycemic properties^{1,2}. The phytochemicals earlier reported from the fresh fruits of *C. indica*^{3,4} includes sitosterol, some common triterpenes and a glycoside of cucurbitacin B. Chemical examination of unripe fruits of *C. indica* collected from our University campus yielded taraxerone in addition to previously reported sitosterol and taraxerol from the petroleum ether extract of the plant material and a white crystalline solid (m.p. 282°) from ethyl acetate extract which appeared to be a glycoside of sitosterol rather than that of cucurbitacin B, as evidenced from the m.p. and tlc behaviour of the glycoside and the derived aglycone. But sitosterol is rarely a homogeneous compound and determination of its exact composition and particularly the configuration of the C-24 alkyl function is important as the latter depends on the taxonomy and evolutionary status of the plant⁵. Though it is generally known that (24*R*)-24-ethylcholest-5-en-3 β -ol is dominant in higher plants, it is in no way exclusive. Further, the presence of diastereoisomeric mixture, presumably due to lack of stereochemical control during the biogenesis or epimerisation of a labile biogenetic intermediate, is known⁶. The close physicochemical properties of C-24 epimeric compounds elude their distinction by simple spectroscopic methods and their resolution by conventional chromatographic techniques. ¹³C nmr spectral analysis and, to a limited extent, high resolution ¹H nmr spectral analysis (200 MHz or

above) are regarded as reliable methods for ascertaining the configuration of the C-24 alkyl function and also for good quantitative analysis of common sitosterol constituents^{6,7}. It has been reported⁶ that resonance signals of carbon atoms at 20 and 23–27 positions of 24*R* isomers differ significantly from the corresponding signals of 24*S* isomers. The isolated glycoside was, therefore, acetylated and the ¹³C nmr spectrum of the resulting tetraacetate was studied and the data clearly revealed it to be an acetylglucoside of (24*R*)-24-ethylcholest-5-en-3 β -ol.

Fresh mature fruits of *C. indica* were cut into slices, sun-dried, pulverised (0.6 kg) and extracted successively with petroleum ether, ethyl acetate and 95% ethanol. The concentrated petroleum ether extract on chromatographic resolution over silica gel from petroleum ether eluate furnished taraxerone, m.p. 236°; $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) 1 710 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃, 80 MHz) 0.83, 0.95, 1.14 (3H, s each), 0.91 (6H, s), 1.07 (9H, s) and 5.6 (1H, dd, *J* 7.8, 3.6 Hz); *m/z* 424 (50), 300 (100), 285 (62), 205 (48), 204 (78), 201 (29), 189 (29), 135 (52) and 107 (58). The benzene eluate furnished in addition to sitosterol (m.p. 135°), a triterpene alcohol, m.p. 276°; [α]_D+4.56° (CHCl₃); *m/z* 426 (31), 411 (20), 302 (100), 287 (57), 204 (97), 189 (23), 135 (53), 121 (40) and 109 (34), which was identified as taraxerol by direct comparison with authentic sample. The ethyl acetate extract on chromatography over silica gel furnished sitosterol glucoside (m.p. 282°) which was proved to be essentially a glucoside of (24*R*)-24-ethylcholest-5-en-3 β -ol from 300 MHz ¹H and 75.5 MHz ¹³C nmr spectral analysis of its tetraacetate (m.p. 152°) prepared by treatment with Ac₂O and pyridine. The resonance signals of the side chain carbons (C-20–C-29) of this tetraacetate were discernible at δ_c 36.1, 18.8, 34.0, 26.2, 45.9, 29.2, 19.1, 19.8, 23.1 and 12.0, in perfect agreement with the reported values⁸.

In spite of the common occurrence of sitosterol glucoside in nature, its isolation is considered important in view of the reported biological activities of its acyl derivatives^{8,9}.

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